

EUFAR Flight Finder & CEDA Satellite Data Finder

Wendy Garland, Richard Smith and Ag Stephens

NCAS/NCEO, Centre for Environmental Data Analysis, RAL Space, STFC, UK

Introduction

Searching for data collected on moving platforms such as research aircraft can be difficult – unless you were involved in the flight planning you are not likely to know where or when a flight took place, or what instruments were operated. The EUFAR Flight Finder tool (EFF) is a geospatial/ temporal/keyword search tool developed during the EUFAR2* FP7 project to maximize discovery, access and re-use of data collected by the many European environmental research aircraft – both atmospheric in-situ and remote-sensing measurements - during EUFAR funded flights whose data are stored in the EUFAR data archive at CEDA.

The capability of this flight-finding tool has been widened to include the full catalogue of flights from the FAAM Bae-146 aircraft and the NERC-Airborne Research Facility (formerly ARSF), also stored in the CEDA archive, and now covers 120TB of data and nearly 2000 flights.

Following the success of the EFF, the concept was adapted and reconfigured to facilitate the discovery of satellite data in the CEDA archives in the CEDA Satellite Finder. This enables geographic and temporal search capability for 2 million Sentinel 1, 2, 3 and Landsat 3, 7, 8 scenes.

How the EFF and Satellite Finder works

Location information -flight tracks, scene coverage-, temporal information, along with parameter and key words have to be extracted from the data files for each flight or scene. Due to the nature of the data involved this is a complex task. It requires identifying, locating and reading specific files for every flight or scene in very diverse datasets. Whilst developing this useful tool several challenges were encountered and overcome (See Challenges box)

Once found, the extracted information is stored in an Elasticsearch database and which can then be easily searched and the results displayed on a user friendly map interface.

The EFF interface, shown on the right, displays FAAM, ARSF and EUFAR flightpaths. Sentinel and Landsat scenes can be found using the CEDA satellite finder shown below.

Using these interfaces the user can refine the search geographically, temporally or for keywords to identify flights/scenes of interest, and then click on the selected flightline/scene for links directly to the data within the appropriate archive.

The screenshot shows the EUFAR Flight Finder web interface. It features a map of Europe with various flight paths overlaid in different colors. A sidebar on the right contains icons for different aircraft types: NERC Dornier, BAS Twin Otters, DLR Dornier, SAFIRE Piper-Jetcab, SAFIRE ATR, DLR Falcon, Skyarrow, and AWI Polar3. Below the map, there are search filters for 'Date in YYYY-MM-DD', 'Geographic search', 'Country', 'Keyword search', and 'Vehicle type'. A URL <http://flight-finder.ceda.ac.uk> is displayed below the map.

Challenges

- Heterogeneous formatting**
Flight data come from 13 aircraft - from as many different sources - each arranged differently and not always consistently. Changes in processing software and layout also occur over time. Many operators have not yet fully achieved the community agreed standard data formats and, even when formats such as NetCDF are used, there can be different "flavour".
- Poor data quality - Erroneous or incomplete data**
These are real scientific measurements - instruments can break or drift - errors are handled/flagged differently by each source. Gaps or inconsistencies that are overlooked or of no consequence to the original user can result in incorrect flight paths or time stamps being displayed and affect the value for re-use.
- Sheer volume of data**
Satellite data are more uniform and the sources fewer, but the volume of files and the number of scenes to scan is immense (currently >2 million scenes, 2.5PB sentinel data)
- Software Maintenance**
As with any operational software, continued maintenance and upgrades are required

The screenshot shows the CEDA Satellite Data Finder web interface. It features a map of Europe with satellite coverage areas overlaid in various colors. A sidebar on the left contains search filters for 'Date in YYYY-MM-DD', 'Geographic search', 'Country', 'Keyword search', and 'Vehicle type'. A URL <http://geo-search.ceda.ac.uk> is displayed below the map.

*What is EUFAR?

The European Facility for Airborne Research in Environmental and Geo-sciences (EUFAR2) (2014-2018) is an Integrating Activity of the 7th Framework Programme (FP7) of the European Commission, following three previous contracts under FP5, FP6 and FP7, bringing together 24 European institutions and organisations involved in airborne research, operating 16 instrumented research aircraft and providing access to a further 3 remote-sensing instruments.

EUFAR facilitates collaboration and cooperation among the aircraft fleet and promotes the use of standards and protocols, and the exchange of knowledge and expertise. It also provides education and training opportunities for early-stage researchers, funded access to state-of-the-art instrumented aircraft not available in a users home country and funded collaborative research projects within the consortium.

www.eufar.net

Conclusions and future plans

The EUFAR Flight Finder and CEDA Satellite Finder tools are now available for use and facilitate discovery and access to 2000 flights and 2 million satellite scenes.

The development of these tools has highlighted the need for well formatted, standardised, consistent datasets in order to maximise the use and re-use of these valuable datasets.

Future plans under consideration include :

- Extending the EFF to display regular (non-EUFAR funded) flights of the wider EUFAR fleet with external links to data sources.
- Including ground-based NCAS observations.
- Adding further Sentinel missions as they are launched by ESA and adding AATSr scenes.
- Improving the search capabilities: keywords, parameters, data products, additional metadata.
- Including a search for co-located satellite and flight data for validation studies

<http://flight-finder.ceda.ac.uk>

<http://geo-search.ceda.ac.uk>

Contact: Wendy Garland
wendy.garland@ncas.ac.uk